

Design principles and techniques for plasmonics and metamaterials

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Abstract

The field of plasmonics and metamaterials has revolutionized the landscape of photonics, offering unprecedented control over light at the nanoscale. This chapter provides a detailed overview of the fundamental concepts, materials, and methodologies essential for advancing these transformative fields. It begins with the basic introduction of plasmonics and metamaterials, focusing on their ability to manipulate light at a very small scale and the resulting technological implications. The chapter further explores materials for plasmonics, including metals, semiconductors, and novel alternatives, highlighting their optical properties and potential for tailored applications. A theoretical framework follows, examining the optical behavior and modes of plasmonic nanostructures to provide a deeper understanding of their interactions with electromagnetic waves. The discussion transitions to metamaterial design principles and strategies, emphasizing resonance tuning, geometry optimization, and functional integration. Finally, the chapter showcases real-world applications, complemented by a case study demonstrating their practical impact in areas such as sensing, energy, and communication. This work serves as a guide for researchers and engineers in the field.

Keywords: Plasmonics, metamaterials, negative refractive index, surface plasmons, sensing

1. Introduction

Surface plasmons are collective oscillations of free charge carriers at the interface of a conductor and a dielectric coupled to an electromagnetic field supported by metallic nanostructures, manifesting themselves either in the form of surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) propagating at the extended conductor dielectric interfaces or as localized surface plasmons (LSPs) present in confined geometries.[1][2] These metallic nanostructures can localize the electromagnetic fields to the deep-subwavelength scales, increasing their local field intensity and significantly enhancing light-matter interactions.[3][4] Therefore, they possess a new realm of possibilities for a variety of applications ranging from biochemical sensing[5][6][7], subdiffraction waveguiding [8], and nonlinear optics[9] to optical modulators[10] and nanolasers.[11] In the last few years, plasmonic nanostructures of different shapes and materials[12] have been developed to achieve an engineered optical response and optimize field localization and enhancement for various applications.

Plasmonics and metamaterials are at the forefront of modern optics and photonics, heralding transformative advancements in the field of science and technology. Plasmonics leverages the

interaction between the electromagnetic waves and the free electrons on the metal's surface, allowing light manipulation at the nanoscale.[13] Metamaterials, conversely, are artificially engineered structures with tuned electromagnetic properties, surpassing those often found in natural materials. Hyperbolic dispersion and negative refractive indices are specific properties of metamaterials that have revolutionized optics and photonics by providing new pathways for light control as well as energy localization.[14] Plasmonic metamaterials, consisting of randomly or periodically arranged plasmonic nanostructures, also called meta-atoms, with a size and spacing much smaller than the interested wavelength, have been widely investigated further enabling the optical performance and the engineering of active functionalities. [15][16] In these artificially structured materials, the size, shape, and spacing of the meta-atoms of the metamaterials determine the macroscopic optical properties, in addition to the optical properties of the constituent material of the meta-atoms. Using different meta-atom designs such as nanospirals, split-ring resonators (SRRs), nanorods etc., the optical response of metamaterials can be tailored with unprecedented degrees of freedom to demonstrate various interesting properties such as negative refractive index,[17] low-frequency plasmons,[18] hyperbolic dispersion,[19] enhanced nonlinear optical response,[20] artificial magnetism,[21] strong optical chirality,[22]. Together, plasmonics and metamaterials form the cornerstone of a new idea in light-matter interaction, with far-reaching implications for fields like imaging, telecommunications, quantum technologies, and sensing.

The importance of plasmonics and metamaterials lies in their ability to break traditional optical limitations, enabling phenomena such as subwavelength focusing, cloaking, superlenses, tunable photonic components, and negative refraction[13]. These capabilities open pathways for ultra-compact photonic devices, efficient energy harvesting systems, and advanced medical diagnostics, among others. As the demand for innovative solutions in areas like high-speed data transfer, sustainable energy, and precision healthcare grows, these technologies offer unparalleled opportunities for advancement. Combined, they underpin technologies ranging from high-resolution imaging and biosensors to quantum information processing and next-generation solar cells. Three-dimensional metamaterials provide advantages compared to one- and two-dimensional metasurfaces[23]. In general, these advantages are attributed to a 3-D structure allowing the degrees of freedom in both transversal and longitudinal directions to be exploited in design. In other words, there are many geometrical parameters to tune the device's behavior. Thus, 3-D metamaterials provide *advanced functionalities* in comparison with 1-D and 2-D counterparts, which may further benefit the future communication systems and smart radio environments[24]. However, the three-dimensional metamaterials are bulkier than planar structures, which can be prohibitive for some purposes. They also demand more excellent computational resources and are significantly more complex to manufacture and, hence, difficult to implement. However, recent years have changed this trend due to the massive technological progress in computer electronics along with the development of 3-D printing techniques.[25] This can be appreciated in Figure 1, where metamaterials of different fields are illustrated.

Figure 1. Examples of different metamaterials- (a–c) Mechanical (d) Acoustic (e) Nanoantenna. (f) Electromagnetic.[26]

However, realizing the full potential of plasmonics and metamaterials is contingent on overcoming significant challenges in their design and fabrication.[27] Precise control over material properties at the nanoscale requires advanced computational models, high-resolution fabrication techniques, and meticulous experimental validation. Issues such as fabrication imperfections, material losses, and scalability further complicate the integration of these technologies into practical applications. Despite their promise, plasmonics and metamaterials face significant challenges. High optical losses in metals, difficulty in fabricating intricate nanostructures, and scalability issues for large-scale applications hinder their widespread deployment.[28] Addressing these challenges requires interdisciplinary collaboration in material science, nanofabrication, and computational modelling.

This chapter comprehensively overviews the fundamental design strategies and fabrication techniques central to plasmonics and metamaterials. It explores the interplay between material properties, geometric configurations, and electromagnetic behavior, offering insights into how theoretical concepts translate into practical implementations. This chapter aims to guide researchers and engineers in developing next-generation photonic devices with applications spanning sensing, imaging, communication, and energy harvesting by bridging the gap between theory and experimentation. It aims to comprehensively understand plasmonics and metamaterials by addressing the challenges and showcasing recent breakthroughs.

2. Materials for Plasmonics

The choice of materials is fundamental to the design and performance of plasmonic devices. Plasmonics exploits the interaction of light with free electrons in materials, resulting in collective oscillations known as surface plasmons. These oscillations are highly sensitive to the electronic properties of the materials involved, particularly the density of free electrons and the dielectric environment.[9] Consequently, selecting appropriate materials is critical to achieving desired plasmonic responses across different wavelength regimes and applications.

2.1. Metals: The Foundation of Plasmonics

Metals have historically served as the cornerstone of plasmonics due to their high density of free electrons, which facilitates strong plasmonic resonances. Among metals, noble metals such as gold (Au) and silver (Ag) are most widely used because of their low optical losses and strong plasmonic behavior in the visible and near-infrared regions of the spectrum.[13]

- Gold (Au): Gold is highly resistant to oxidation and corrosion, making it a stable choice for plasmonic applications. It exhibits strong plasmonic resonances in the visible to near-infrared range. However, its optical losses in the blue and ultraviolet (UV) regions limit its efficiency for shorter wavelengths.[29]
- Silver (Ag): Silver is the most efficient plasmonic material due to its minimal optical losses and high-quality factor in the visible spectrum. However, its susceptibility to oxidation and tarnishing can degrade its performance, necessitating protective coatings or encapsulation strategies.[30]
- Aluminum (Al): Aluminum has gained attention for its plasmonic behavior in the ultraviolet (UV) spectrum. Its abundance and low cost make it an attractive alternative for applications requiring UV plasmonics, although its higher losses in the visible range limit its broader applicability.[31]
- Copper (Cu): While less common, copper exhibits plasmonic properties similar to gold and silver but at a lower cost. However, its susceptibility to oxidation and relatively higher losses often necessitate additional surface treatments.[32]

2.2. Emerging Alternatives: Beyond Traditional Metals

The limitations of noble metals, including their high cost and optical losses, have spurred interest in alternative materials for plasmonics. These materials offer tailored properties that can expand the scope of plasmonic applications.

- Transparent Conducting Oxides (TCOs): Materials such as indium tin oxide (ITO) and aluminum-doped zinc oxide (AZO) exhibit plasmonic behavior in the near-infrared to mid-infrared regions.[33] Their tunable optical properties and compatibility with transparent substrates make them ideal for applications in telecommunications and sensing.
- Transition Metal Nitrides: Materials like titanium nitride (TiN) and zirconium nitride (ZrN) have gained attention as plasmonic alternatives to noble metals. They exhibit good plasmonic performance in the visible and near-infrared regions, coupled with

superior thermal stability and mechanical robustness, making them suitable for high-temperature applications.[34]

- Graphene and 2D Materials: Graphene supports plasmonic resonances in the terahertz to mid-infrared range due to its unique electronic properties.[35] Its tunability via electrical gating and chemical doping makes it a promising candidate for dynamic plasmonic devices. Other 2D materials, such as MXenes and black phosphorus, also show potential for specific plasmonic applications.[36]

2.3. Dielectrics and Semiconductors for Hybrid Plasmonic Systems

Combining metals with dielectric or semiconductor materials can enhance plasmonic performance by mitigating losses and enabling hybrid modes. Dielectrics such as silicon dioxide (SiO₂) or titanium dioxide (TiO₂) are commonly used as insulating layers or substrates, while semiconductors like silicon (Si) and gallium arsenide (GaAs) facilitate integration with photonic and electronic devices.

- Doped Semiconductors: Highly doped semiconductors, including indium arsenide (InAs) and silicon carbide (SiC), exhibit plasmonic behavior in the mid-infrared region, offering new avenues for applications in thermal imaging and infrared sensing.

2.4. Key Considerations for Material Selection

When selecting materials for plasmonic applications, several factors must be considered:

1. Optical Losses: Minimizing absorption and scattering losses is critical for achieving efficient plasmonic resonances.
2. Stability: Long-term performance requires materials that resist oxidation, corrosion, and thermal degradation.
3. Fabrication Compatibility: The chosen material must be compatible with the fabrication techniques and underlying substrates used in the device.
4. Cost and Scalability: For large-scale applications, the availability and cost-effectiveness of the material play significant roles.
5. Spectral Range: Different materials exhibit plasmonic behavior in specific wavelength ranges, necessitating alignment with application requirements.

3. Theoretical Frameworks - Optical properties and modes of plasmonic nanostructures

A robust theoretical framework is essential for understanding and designing plasmonic and metamaterial systems. These frameworks provide the mathematical and physical principles governing electromagnetic wave interaction with nanostructures and engineered materials. By leveraging these principles, researchers can predict optical responses, optimize device performance, and guide fabrication processes.

3.1. Localized surface plasmons (LSPs)

The nanoparticles in a plasmonic metallic structure usually support LSPR mode, in which the free electrons collectively oscillate with the incident light at a specific frequency.[37] [38][39] In this case, the optical extinction of the metal absorption cross-section C_{abs} and the nanoparticle's scattering cross-section C_{sca} would reach the maximum value at the resonant wavelength.[40] For a homogenous sphere metal nanoparticle with a size smaller than 100 nm, the C_{abs} and C_{sca} can usually be expressed as follows[41]

$$C_{sca} = \frac{8\pi}{3} k^4 a^6 \left[\frac{\epsilon_m - \epsilon_d}{\epsilon_m + 2\epsilon_d} \right]^2 \quad (3.1)$$

$$C_{abs} = 4\pi k a^3 \text{Im} \left[\frac{\epsilon_m - \epsilon_d}{\epsilon_m + 2\epsilon_d} \right] \quad (3.2)$$

Where, ϵ_m and a are the dielectric function and radius of the metallic nanoparticle, k is the incident light wave vector of the incident light, and ϵ_d is the dielectric constant of the surrounding environment. It can be inferred that when $|\epsilon_m + 2\epsilon_d|$ is a minimum, both C_{sca} and C_{abs} reach the maximum values, leading to very sharp absorption and scattering peaks in the provided LSPR spectrum.

From Equations (3.1) and (3.2), it is worth noting that LSPR is significantly affected by the composition, the nanoparticle's size, and the environment's dielectric constant.[38] It can be inferred that both the above equations are derived for the spherical nanoparticles. The LSPR modes depend on the nanoparticles' shape with distinct characteristics with the number of resonance peaks determined by the number of polarization modes.[42] Hence, nonspherical nanoparticles generally exhibit more resonance peaks than spherical particles.[12] For example, a nanorod particle can be polarized along two axes. Therefore, it usually shows two peaks, i.e., transverse and longitudinal resonance modes in the given LSPR spectrum.[43] The plasmonic performance of metals can be described by the plasmonic quality factor Q given as[38]

$$Q = -\frac{\epsilon_r}{\epsilon_i} \quad (3.3)$$

where ϵ_r and ϵ_i are the real and image parts of ϵ_m , respectively; since ϵ_r and ϵ_i values of metal materials are highly dependent on the wavelength, choosing suitable metals for the plasmonic nanostructures is important to ensure Q is maximum in the optical range.[44] Silver is a plasmonic material with small losses with resonance peaks in the visible region with a high Q value.[44][45] However, Ag gets oxidized quickly. Alternatively, Au is another vastly used plasmonic material in visible region with excellent chemical stability and high plasmonic performance under ambient conditions.[46] However, for the nanostructures in UV region, Al is an excellent choice due to its high Q . [47] Besides achieving the maximum optical extinction, the metal nanoparticle's near field also greatly enhances at the resonant frequency.[38] This is due to two main effects.[41] The first one is the localized surface plasmon resonant excitations, which produce mainly a dipolar field near the nanoparticle and are strongly frequency-dependent.[41] The second contribution is due to the lightning rod effect, which is purely a geometric phenomenon of field line crowding, resulting in enhancement near sharp metallic features.[48] The highly enhanced near-field causes plasmonic nanoparticles leads to

vast applications in various fields, such as surface-enhanced spectroscopies.[49][50][51] and nonlinear optics.[52]

3.2. Surface plasmon polaritons (SPP)

The periodic array of metal nanoparticles makes it possible to excite SPP mode by coupling the momentum of incident light and SPP wave .[53] For a 1D metallic array, SPP can be excited with the following condition satisfied[54]

$$k_{spp} = k_0 \sin\theta \pm v \frac{2\pi}{a} \quad (3.4)$$

where k_{spp} and k_0 are the SPP and incident light wave vectors, respectively. θ is the incident angle, v is the integral number, and a is the array period. Similarly, for a 2D plasmonic array with periods in x and y directions, Equation (3.4) is modified as[55]

$$k_{spp} = k_0 \sin\theta \pm iG_x \pm iG_y \quad (3.5)$$

where G_x and G_y are the Bragg vectors linked with the two grating periods, i and j are the grating orders for both G_x and G_y , respectively. From the above two equations, we observe that SPP is modulated by the value of incident angle as well as the morphology and the period of the plasmonic array.[56] Additionally, unlike the LSPR mode, SPP can propagate along the surface of the nanostructures on the order of several hundreds of micrometers.[57] The corresponding propagation length (L_{spp}) can be given as[57]

$$L_{SPP} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} \left[\frac{\epsilon_d + \epsilon_r}{\epsilon_d \epsilon_r} \right]^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (3.6)$$

Where ϵ_d is the dielectric constant of the surrounding environment and ϵ_r is the real part of metallic dielectric constant. In addition to the excitation of SPP mode, metallic nanostructured plasmonic arrays can also be employed as metal gratings generating diffraction light of varying orders

3.3. Fabry Perot cavity Mode (F-P modes)

Multiple stacked plasmonic nanostructured arrays may lead to F–P cavity modes. For the simplest three-layer structure with two metallic mirrors with an optically transparent dielectric medium, the constructive interference may occur in the dielectric cavity. Similarly, for the N th mode excited in the F–P cavity, the wavelength can be calculated as follows with the direction of propagation of the incident light perpendicular to the metallic nanostructures.[58][59]

$$\lambda_N = \frac{2n_d(d+\delta)}{N} \quad (3.7)$$

where n_d is the real part of the refractive index of the cavity dielectric, d is the distance between the two mirrors, and δ represents the increased cavity length due to the reflection phase. The resonance wavelength of F–P cavity strongly depends on the cavity thickness.

If one of the metallic mirrors is replaced by a plasmonic structure with a larger linewidth, the effective coupling can be achieved when the following resonance condition is fulfilled[58]

$$\Delta\varphi_{tot} = 2\Delta\varphi_{prop} + \Delta\varphi_{ref} + \Delta\varphi_{exc} = 2\pi N \quad (3.8)$$

where $\Delta\varphi_{tot}$ is the total phase shift during a complete wave roundtrip in the cavity, $\Delta\varphi_{prop}$ is the phase shift due to the wave propagation in the cavity and is highly dependent on the cavity thickness, $\Delta\varphi_{ref}$ is the phase shift on reflection at the cavity mirror and can be obtained using the Fresnel equations, $\Delta\varphi_{exc}$ is the phase shift of the plasmonic excitation depending on the RI of the analyte.

3.4 Gap Mode

A gap mode can be generated via near-field coupling when a metal nanoparticle is close to a metallic film or any other metallic nanoparticle.[58] In comparison with a single nanoparticle, the nanoparticle in the gap mode shows a redshift in their resonance mode as the presence of an adjacent metal film or metallic nanoparticle will weaken the restoring force acting on the metallic nanostructure electrons.[60] Additionally, the near-field in the gap can also be greatly enhanced due to the strong localization of the light energy in a small space.[61] This is why the ultrahigh sensitivity is down to a single molecule for SERS analysis.[62][63] The interaction strength of metallic nanoparticles increases with the decrease in the distance between them. Hence, distance control is very essential for the manipulation of gap mode.

In the case of a metallic nanoparticle, which can be regarded as a dipole–metal, a dipole with an opposite charge distribution can be induced in the metallic film. Therefore, the two opposite-direction dipoles can be considered as an antisymmetric mode, causing magnetic resonance in the nanostructure, which may facilitate perfect light absorption.[64]

3.5. Plasmonic Fano Resonance

Fano resonance is one of the quantum interference phenomena due to the interaction of a discrete state with a continuum.[65] Unlike Lorentzian resonance, Fano resonance shows spectral profiles which are distinctly asymmetric, given by Fano formula[66]

$$\sigma(\epsilon) = \frac{D^2(q+\Omega)^2}{1+\Omega^2} \quad (3.9)$$

where $D^2 = 4\sin^2\delta$ (with δ as the phase shift of the continuum), E is the energy, $q = \cot\delta$ is known as the Fano parameter determining the degree of asymmetry, and $\Omega = \frac{2(E-E_0)}{\Gamma}$ is the resonance width and E_0 is the energy).

Fano resonance have also been noticed in clusters of plasmonic nanoparticles[67] and the nanostructures with the symmetry breaking[68], with the sharp or broad subradiant resonance modes typically showing the high-order modes.[69] in plasmonic Fano resonance, high spectral contrast with narrow asymmetric profile can be obtained by lineshape engineering.[70] Additionally, the near-field of the nanostructure can also be highly enhanced at the required frequency. The enhanced near-field and the narrow bandwidth allow plasmonic Fano resonance wide applications in plasmonic sensors, metamaterials, nanolasers, optoelectronic devices, etc.[71]

4. Metamaterial Design Principles and strategy

4.1. Plasmonic metamaterials to implement negative refraction and negative refractive index

The negative refractive index is the basis of metamaterials. In 1968, Victor G. Veselago published a theoretical paper studying the fundamentals of negative refractive index[72]. He showed that if the relative magnetic permeability (μ_r) and the relative electric permittivity (ϵ_r) are simultaneously negative, then the refractive index of the material as well has to be negative, that is,

$$n = -\sqrt{|\epsilon_r||\mu_r|} \quad (4.1)$$

Such a negative-index material (NIM) does not occur naturally; however, it exhibits many interesting properties. For instance, it can be proven from Maxwell's equations that for a plane wave propagation in a NIM, electric field \vec{E} , magnetic field \vec{H} and the wave vector \vec{k} , follow the left-hand rule and wave vector \vec{k} and Poynting vector \vec{S} are antiparallel to each other. This is in contrast to a positive-index material, in which \vec{E} , \vec{H} and \vec{k} form right-handed triplet with \vec{k} and \vec{S} are parallel each other.

These NIMs strongly illustrate unusual electromagnetic properties. For example, the Doppler effect, Snell's law, radiation pressure, and Cherenkov effect are reversed in NIMs[72]. Starting with Snell's law, as illustrated in Figure 3A, when the light wave is incident from a positive-refractive index material to a NIM, the refracted light falls on the same side as the incident light with respect to the normal of the surface. This is in order to conserve the tangential components of the wave vectors for the incident and refracted light, with energy flowing away from the interface (causality principle). From Snell's law

Figure 2. (a) Schematic showing negative refraction when light wave is incident from a positive-index material to an NIM. For a negative-index material, the wave vector \vec{k} and the Poynting vector \vec{S} are antiparallel to each other. The wave patterns (in blue and red color) are from obtained using full-wave simulation. (b) Pictorial image of an NIM metamaterial working at microwave frequencies having copper wires and SRRs. (c) SEM image of a 3D fishnet structure to obtain bulk NIMs at the optical frequencies. The inset shows alternating layers of 30 nm Ag and 50 nm MgF₂ [13]

$$\frac{\sin \theta_i}{\sin \theta_r} = \frac{n_r}{n_i} \quad (4.2)$$

the angle of refraction has to be negative when the refractive indices of the two materials possess opposite signs.

Negative refraction and NIM's were first studied experimentally at the microwave frequencies with Cu wire arrays and split ring resonators which simultaneously implemented negative permittivity and permeability (Figure 2(b))[73] sparking a breakthrough in global metamaterial research. Since then, tremendous efforts have been made to scale down and optimize the size of the metamaterial design, enabling its operation at higher frequencies. The metamaterial's size needs to be of the order of 100 nm or even smaller for working at optical frequencies, creating considerable fabrication difficulty. So far, the most widely studied NIMs are the fishnet structure[74], which is significantly easy to fabricate. The fishnet metamaterials comprise two layers of metallic meshes separated by a dielectric layer, with the paired stripes aligned parallel to the electric field, providing negative permittivity. In contrast, the other stripes parallel to the magnetic field provide negative permeability. This arrangement is much simpler than NIMs by combining split resonators and metallic wires. (Figure 2(c), For example, Xiang Zhang's group studied the negative refractive index by stacking 11 functional layers of fishnet structures through broadband and low-loss NIMs at near-infrared wavelengths.[75] Hence, active optical and loss-free NIMs in the visible region are achieved by incorporating gain material into the fishnet structure.[76]

Engineering the propagation of SPPs provides another approach to realizing negative refractive indices and NIMs. For instance, for small dielectric layer thickness, there are two bound-SPP modes in 2D metal-dielectric-metal (MDM) waveguide slab, originating from the hybridization and coupling of the SPP mode at each metal-dielectric interface.[77] For instance, Verhagen et al. demonstrated theoretically that a metamaterial has a 3D negative refractive index at visible frequencies by stacking an array of MDM waveguides[78]. In his design, the unit cell comprises a pair of strongly coupled MDM waveguides with the eigenmodes resembling odd and even superpositions of the antisymmetric mode in each MDM waveguide. The odd superposition shows a negative coupling coefficient and a negative mode wave vector, creating negative energy and phase refractive index for the transverse magnetic (TM) polarized light. Hence, an isotropic negative refractive index can provide wave propagation in these 3D metamaterials. The transformation optics approach has recently been used to map the plasmonic waveguide in a crescent-shaped plasmonic resonator in order to degenerate magnetic and electric dipoles[79]. Numerical simulations indicate that a periodic array of these resonators shows a negative refractive index over 200 nm wavelength bandwidth at given optical frequencies. The negative refractive index and near-zero refractive index have also been indicated in the planar MDM waveguide[80] and the crescent plasmonic structure[79] in the optical range.

In addition, various groups have attempted to achieve isotropic NIMs by using the Mie resonance of the core-shell nanostructures. From the Mie theory, a nanoparticle can support electric as well as magnetic multipolar modes with the particle's electromagnetic scattering and extinction efficiencies originating from all the modes. The magnetic dipole resonance is, in general, weaker than the electric dipole mode. Still, a structure made of high-permittivity material can significantly enhance it[81], which includes certain semiconductors. Some of the

properly designed core-shell structures demonstrate a negative refractive index by the overlapping of the electric and magnetic resonances within the same spectral range. The core metallic part is responsible for the electric plasmon response, while the semiconductor shell provides a strong magnetic resonance with the negative permeability. Numerical simulations further verified that core-shell nanowires and nanoparticles can implement NIMs in the near-infrared region[82]. Therefore, NIMs formed from core-shell nanoparticles exhibit both isotropic and polarization-independent properties due to the spherical symmetry of the constituents. Experimental verification of such NIMs has not been done yet, although a strong magnetic response has been obtained in a typical plasmonic core-shell geometry[83].

Finally, we shall briefly describe the reversal of Cherenkov effect and the Doppler effect NIMs[72]. The Cherenkov effect is due to the electromagnetic radiation of a charged particle when it travels in a given medium faster than the phase velocity of the light in the given medium[84]. In conventional materials with a positive refractive index, the radiation falls in an expanding cone in the given forward direction of the movement, whereas, in NIMs, the radiation direction is reversed to the backward side[85]. Similarly, the inverse Doppler effect occurs while observing a source traveling in a NIM. The experimental observations and demonstration of the two effects are more challenging than negative refraction. The reversed Cherenkov radiation's power reaches a maximum in the UV region and drops rapidly with the increasing wavelengths[86]. The presently available optical metamaterials are still very lossy and not suitable for detecting weak radiation signals. Even in microwave regimes where both the detection and the fabrication techniques are well established, only recently researchers have reported the first observation of the reversed Cherenkov radiation[87][86]. However, certain groups have earlier presented indirect evidence[88] and analogous[89]. The main difficulty for the inverse Doppler effect originates from measuring the frequency shift inside the media. So far, very few experimental observations of the inverse Doppler effect are based on the nonlinear transmission lines at THz[90] and photonic crystals with effective negative refractive indices at the optical frequencies[91]. However, the demonstration of the inverse Doppler effect employing NIMs is still lacking.

4.2. Chiral Metamaterials

An object possesses chirality when it cannot be superimposed with its mirror image.[92] Chiral metamaterial is an important metamaterial for tuning molecular interactions. Some classical examples of chiral structures would be the right and left hands or a simple elastic spring (Figure 3(a)). Chirality is easily found in nature in various areas, from the chemical molecule configuration to the spin of elementary particles.[93] Right and left circular polarizations (LCP and RCP) are light's two fundamental chiral states in electromagnetism. Optical materials can also possess chirality, resulting in different optical properties for circularly polarized light with different handedness. Specifically, this results in optical birefringence, which occurs when left circularly polarized (LCP) and right circularly polarized (RCP) light travel through a medium at different rates (this is linked to the distinct real parts of their refractive indices), and circular dichroism (CD), when LCP and RCP light states are absorbed differently.[94][95] This is associated with the varying imaginary parts of their refractive indices. Collectively, these two phenomena are known as the optical activity of the medium. From a phenomenological

perspective, the chirality of the material indicates that its electric and magnetic responses are interrelated.

$$\vec{D} = \epsilon_0 \vec{E} - i \frac{Q\vec{H}}{c} \quad (4.3)$$

$$\vec{B} = \mu_0 \mu \vec{H} - i \frac{Q\vec{E}}{c} \quad (4.4)$$

where Q is the chirality parameter. As the magnetic response of natural materials at optical frequencies is very weak, their chiral optical properties are also weak: light has to travel macroscopic distances through the media in order to achieve pronounced optical activity effects.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of chiral metamaterial. (a) Basic chiral structures (b) One of the possible chiral plasmonic metamaterial design fabricated using physical deposition method providing the helical channels.[96]

Metamaterials present a unique technology that significantly improves media's electric and magnetic responses, particularly by leveraging resonant effects. This capability makes them an excellent foundation for developing optical materials with substantially enhanced chiral characteristics. In this context, numerous designs of chiral metamaterials have been realized, with spirally shaped metallic nanowires serving as a quintessential example (Figure 3(b)). Subsequently, artificial optical materials exhibit remarkably enhanced circular dichroism (CD)

and birefringence, surpassing the performance of natural materials by several orders of magnitude.

Chiral metamaterials can form a strong optical chirality in the near-field. Hence, they serve as an important platform for chiral-based sensing of biomolecules. [97][98]. Optical excitations of plasmonic chiral metamaterials generate superchiral electromagnetic fields, which are quite sensitive probes of the chirality of the supermolecular structures[99]. For instance, right- and left-handed gold gammadion arrays were fabricated on a glass substrate (inset of Figure 4(a)) with their CD spectra essentially mirror images of each other (Figure 4(a)). Three different resonance modes (I, II, and III) in the CD spectra refer to the excitation of LSPs in the metamaterials. Upon the monolayer adsorption of chiral molecules (β -lactoglobulin, which possess high levels of β -sheet based secondary structure) onto the surface of the left- and right-handed gold gammadion arrays, the strong coupling between the chiral molecules and the chiral-shaped gammadions led to the dissymmetrical shift of the metamaterial resonances $\delta\Delta\lambda = \Delta\lambda_{RH} - \Delta\lambda_{LH} \approx 16$ nm, where $\Delta\lambda_{LH}$ and $\Delta\lambda_{RH}$ are the shift in wavelength of the LSP modes for the right and the left-handed metamaterials (Figure 4(b)). In contrast, for the heat-treated β -lactoglobulin, a smaller dissymmetry ($\delta\Delta\lambda \approx 0$) was observed (Figure 4(c)). The disparity in the effective refractive indices of chiral samples for left- and right-handed metamaterials in superchiral fields of opposing handedness was as much as 10^6 times greater than the values recorded in optical polarimetry measurements.[97][100] This significant difference facilitates the characterization of picogram quantities of absorbed molecules. This methodology allows for the differentiation of proteins based on varying β -sheet content. Subsequent research has shown that chiral plasmonic metamaterials, such as Shuriken metamaterials, can detect higher-order hierarchical structures of proteins at the pictogram level, as well as proteins with similar structures that differ by a single amino acid in their primary sequences, and the structural organization of proteins within complex bio-interfaces.

Figure 4. Chiral sensing using plasmonic metamaterials. (a) CD spectra of left- and right-handed gold gammadion arrays. Insets indicate the SEM images of the chiral metamaterials (b) Effect of the absorbed proteins β -lactoglobulin and the denatured β -lactoglobulin on the CD spectra of metamaterials. Red spectra were obtained in Tris buffer before the protein adsorption (solid line indicate the left-hand chiral metamaterial; dashed line shows the right-handed metamaterial), black spectra were obtained after the protein adsorption. (c) SEM image and illustration of a metamaterial twisted by an angle of +60°. (d) CD spectra of the metamaterial in (c) after functionalization with a monolayer of protein (Concanavalin A) for metamaterials twisted by $\pm 60^\circ$. [96]

The application of left- and right-handed twisted optical metamaterials (refer to Figure 24c) has enabled the ultrasensitive detection of chiral molecules at the zeptomole scale, achieved without any dependence on spectral shifts. This accomplishment was made possible by aggregating the measurements from the enantiomeric pair of metamaterial substrates, both functionalized with identical analytes, thereby eliminating the substantial background circular dichroism (CD) signals from the metamaterial and negating its effective influence on the resultant CD response. As illustrated in Figure 24d, CD measurements of a monolayer of Concanavalin A proteins, which were spin-coated onto $\pm 60^\circ$ twisted optical metamaterials, reveal a distinct dip in the Σ CD (represented by blue diamonds) towards negative values around a wavelength of 970 nm, signifying the left-handed characteristic of the proteins. The concentration of the molecules detected within the imaging area was as low as approximately 55 zeptomoles, equating to about 44 molecules per unit cell of the metamaterial, which is 10^{15} times lower than the detection limits of conventional commercial CD spectroscopy instruments.

Recently, gold nanohelicoids synthesized using methods like seed-mediated growth or amino acid/peptides-assisted synthesis can achieve precise chiral geometries and exceptional optical activity[101][102]These features make them suitable for applications in polarization control, chiral sensing, and chiral plasmon-driven photocatalysis[103].

4.3. Metamaterials with Hyperbolic Dispersion

The vectorial characteristics of the electromagnetic field imply that the propagation of light within an anisotropic medium is influenced by both the direction of propagation and the polarization state.[104][105] In general, for any given direction of propagation, there exist two linearly polarized eigenwaves that maintain their polarization state throughout the propagation process, although they possess distinct refractive indices, n , as determined by the solutions to Fresnel's equation concerning wave normals.

$$\frac{s_x^2}{n^2-n_x^2} + \frac{s_y^2}{n^2-n_y^2} + \frac{s_z^2}{n^2-n_z^2} \quad (4.5)$$

where (s_x, s_y, s_z) is the unit vector along the direction of the wave vector \mathbf{k} and $n_x = \sqrt{\epsilon_{xx}}$, $n_y = \sqrt{\epsilon_{yy}}$ and $n_z = \sqrt{\epsilon_{zz}}$ are the refractive indices along the three optical axes of the material. The situation is much simpler for uniaxial optical materials having a specific axis with a refractive index $n_e = n_{\parallel}$ (called the optical axis). In contrast, the refractive indices for the other two directions are equal: $n_o = n_{\perp}$ (with the subscripts indicating the angle between the optic axis and the considered direction). Here, the electromagnetic wave propagating in the material is divided into two parts: ordinary, having polarization perpendicular to the optic axis with the refractive index n_o independent of the direction of their wave vector

$$\frac{k^2}{n_o^2} = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \quad (4.6)$$

and extraordinary with the propagation constant dependent on the propagation direction so that their wave vectors are represented by an ellipsoid in the k -space, Figure 5:

$$\frac{k_x^2}{n_e^2} + \frac{k_y^2}{n_e^2} + \frac{k_z^2}{n_o^2} = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \quad (4.7)$$

Figure 5. Transformation of dispersion of the extraordinary waves from (a) the elliptical for uniaxial optical materials to hyperbolic for plasmonic metamaterials of (b) Type I and (c) Type II in the lossless case. Both Type I and Type II metamaterials can be obtained with either multilayer structures or nanowires as indicated.[96]

Two examples of uniaxial plasmonic metamaterials can be identified. The first example is a nanorod metamaterial, created from an array of vertically aligned metallic nanowires with diameters ranging from approximately 20 to 50 nm, spacings of about 50 to 100 nm, and lengths between 20 and 500 nm. This type of metamaterial is typically fabricated through electrodeposition into a porous dielectric matrix. The second example is a multilayer metamaterial formed by stacking alternating layers of dielectric and metallic materials with standard thicknesses of around 10 to 30 nm, utilizing conventional thin-layer deposition methods. By applying effective medium theories that involve averaging the electric field vectors E and D over the volume, one can calculate the effective permittivities for both the nanorod and multilayer metamaterials, noting that the effective permeabilities will equal 1 due to the lack of any natural or artificial magnetic response.

$$\varepsilon_{eff,\parallel} = (1 - f)\varepsilon_d + f\varepsilon_m \quad (4.8)$$

$$\varepsilon_{eff,\perp} = \frac{\varepsilon_d(1-p)\varepsilon_d + (1+p)\varepsilon_m}{(1+p)\varepsilon_d + (1-p)\varepsilon_m} \quad (4.9)$$

Where, ϵ_m ϵ_d are the permittivities of the metal and dielectric, respectively, while $f = \pi d^2 / (4p^2 \sin(\pi/3))$ is the metal filling factor calculated in this case of hexagonal array, d is the diameter of the nanowire, and p is the periodicity of array. For the multilayer hyperbolic metamaterial, the EMT results in

$$\epsilon_{eff,\parallel} = \frac{\epsilon_m \epsilon_d}{(1-f)\epsilon_d + f\epsilon_m} \quad (4.10)$$

$$\epsilon_{eff,\perp} = (1-f)\epsilon_d + f\epsilon_m \quad (4.11)$$

where $f = t_m / (t_d + t_m)$ is the metal filling factor calculated for the structure with thicknesses t_m and t_d for the metal and dielectric, respectively[106]. By adjusting the frequency-dependent permittivities of the dielectric (positive) and metal (negative) in conjunction with the structural geometrical parameters, it is feasible to create a scenario where the real parts of ϵ_{\parallel} and ϵ_{\perp} exhibit opposite signs, initially considering a lossless condition. This seemingly straightforward alteration leads to significant transformations in the metamaterial dispersions. The dispersions of extraordinary (TM-polarized) waves transition from a confined elliptical shape to an unbounded hyperboloid (refer to Figure 5). Both type I ($\epsilon_{\parallel} < 0$, $\epsilon_{\perp} > 0$, as shown in Figure 5b) and type II ($\epsilon_{\parallel} > 0$, $\epsilon_{\perp} < 0$, illustrated in Figure 5c) hyperbolic dispersions can be realized through either nanowire or multilayer configurations, contingent upon the selected material and geometrical parameters (see Figures 5b and c). Consequently, as indicated by the dispersions, the metamaterial begins to support optical modes characterized by arbitrarily large wave vectors situated near the cones defined by the hyperboloid asymptotes. It is important to note that these conclusions are derived from the optical parameters obtained through the metamaterial homogenization approach and effective medium theories (EMTs), which are based on specific assumptions. Notably, the nanostructuring is presumed to be subwavelength, a condition that holds true only for wave vectors of the metamaterial modes that are smaller than approximately $1/a$, where a represents the period of the nanostructuring. This assumption imposes limitations on the applicability of the theory and its findings in k-space. Additionally, the inevitable presence of losses in the metal will alter the dispersion hyperbolas into finite hyperbola-like surfaces.

We present an example concerning the optical response of nanorod metamaterials, as illustrated in Figure 6. By employing a conventional (local) version of the effective medium theory (EMT) previously discussed, one can derive the tensor components of the anisotropic permittivity, as shown in Figure 6(b). For the selected geometric parameters and materials, the real parts of the permittivity components perpendicular to the optical axis remain consistently positive. In contrast, the corresponding component aligned with the optical axis exhibits a sign change at a wavelength near 700 nm. This spectral range is referred to as the epsilon-near-zero (ENZ) region, which holds significance for various applications that will be elaborated upon later. Furthermore, the ENZ wavelength serves as a boundary that distinguishes the optical response of the metamaterial into elliptical (short-wavelength) and hyperbolic (long-wavelength) regions. It is important to note the limitations of the EMT for perfectly periodic structures when the spacing between the nanorods approaches the wavelength of the propagating mode, leading to the emergence of diffraction effects. In

metals with reduced losses, the double-bend observed in the spectral behavior of $\text{Re}[\epsilon_{\text{eff},\perp}(\omega)]$ can exhibit a greater amplitude, dipping below zero and consequently resulting in two ENZ points for $\epsilon_{\text{eff},\perp}$, along with another type of hyperbolic dispersion within the spectral range between them. When analyzing (or measuring) the transmission through a layer of nanorod metamaterial, two extinction peaks can be identified, as depicted in Figure 3c. The peak at shorter wavelengths corresponds to the condition $\text{Re}[\epsilon_{\text{eff},\perp}(\omega)] \rightarrow \infty$ (in the absence of losses), while the longer wavelength peak aligns with the ENZ point where $\text{Re}[\epsilon_{\text{eff},\parallel}(\omega)] \rightarrow 0$. The peak associated with $\epsilon_{\text{eff},\perp}$ is observed for both s- and p-polarized waves, as both possess an electric field component perpendicular to the optical axis. Conversely, the long-wavelength peak is only detected under p-polarized illumination, where the electric field component is oriented along the optical axis, thus interacting with ϵ_{\parallel} .

Figure 6. Gold nanorod metamaterial's optical response. (a) Field mapping of the intensity and E_x component of electric field inside the nanorod in the hyperbolic dispersion region excited at an oblique light incidence (b) Real and imaginary part of the relative permittivity of the plasmonic nanorod metamaterial showing gold nanorods in an alumina matrix in a hexagonal array with the diameter 30 nm and the periodicity 80 nm calculated using a local EMT. (c) Extinction curve of the metamaterial, and (d) reflectivity of a metamaterial layer having a thickness of 450 nm.[107]

The two extinction peaks previously discussed delineate the spectral regions in which the metamaterial exhibits opacity. Concurrently, hyperbolic metamaterial slabs are capable of supporting Fabry–Perot and guided modes. The spectral characteristics of these modes are often not distinctly visible in the extinction spectra due to the overwhelming intensity of the extinction peaks; however, they can be identified as minima or maxima in transmission and, more notably, in reflection (refer to Figure 6d), contingent upon the specific geometrical parameters of the sample. The guided modes within the metamaterial slab can be utilized for the engineering of molecular emission[108] or for the enhancement of second harmonic generation[109]. Additionally, a two-dimensional counterpart of hyperbolic metamaterials, known as hyperbolic metasurfaces, has been successfully developed for surface plasmon polariton (SPP) waves[14]. In summary, the hyperbolic effect induced by the metamaterial can be significantly pronounced and has been experimentally validated, leading to applications in subwavelength microscopy and lithography, control of thermal and spontaneous emission, ultrafast optical modulation, lasing, and sensing[110], many of which will be elaborated upon in the context of metamaterials that are functionalized with molecules.

5. Applications and Case Study

5.1. Invisibility cloaking

A completely invisible cloak has the same scattering feature as a vacuum. The main goal of cloaking is to hide an object from being detected by radar or any other detection method. This can be done when an electromagnetic wave hitting the object to be hidden passes through the cloak without being reflected or scattered by that object, meaning the electromagnetic field should curve around the object. The creation of a cloak involves transformation optics (TO), where a conformal coordinate change is applied to the Maxwell's equations to produce a spatially varied set of parameters that define the cloak. The permeability and permittivity tensors[111] of the cloak material are formulated so that the material becomes spatially constant, inhomogeneous and anisotropic, which are the necessary properties to achieve cloaking.

Permittivity tensor,

$$\varepsilon' = \Lambda \varepsilon \Lambda^T / \det(\Lambda) \quad (5.1)$$

Permeability tensor,

$$\mu' = \Lambda \mu \Lambda^T / \det(\Lambda) \quad (5.2)$$

where, ε and μ are permittivity and permeability of free space respectively, and Λ is the Jacobian transformation tensor with components, $\Lambda_{ij} = dx_i / dx_j$ (5.3) Therefore, a volume of free space is converted into a shell-type region using the coordinate transformation, which may hide the object inside the shell from incident a multilayer structure of radius b , and the object which shall be cloaked is shown as a PEC cylinder with radius a (Figure (7(a))).

Figure 7. (a) Illustration of cylindrical cloak. (b) A flexible metamaterial designed and fabricated for cloaking applications[112]

The pioneering 2D metamaterial cloak developed by Schurig and colleagues in 2006 exhibited certain deficiencies attributed to material absorption and estimation inaccuracies. The implementation of the conformal mapping technique mitigated these deficiencies, facilitating the pursuit of ideal invisibility within the constraints of geometric optics. A coordinate transformation method was employed to engineer a non-magnetic cylindrical cloak designed for optical wavelengths, aimed at concealing substantial objects. Furthermore, more sophisticated transformations were applied to eliminate undesirable scattering associated with the optical frequency of the cloaked object. While the coordinate transformation method holds potential for designing broadband cloaking, it is important to note that the cloak's efficacy diminishes as losses increase. It is also possible to construct a cloak that obscures objects situated within it, wherein both the concealed object and its surrounding environment can be optically neutralized through the use of a complementary media layer that contains the complementary image of the object, known as the anti-object. This concept may also be interpreted as an inverse cloak. The benefit of this cloak is that it operates effectively for all polarizations at once. Achieving broadband cloaking of light may be accomplished through concentric cylindrical layers using a scaling transformation (ST). Wavelength multiplexing served as the foundational idea for realizing broadband cloaking. Flexible metamaterials have been demonstrated on free-standing polyimide substrates operating at terahertz (THz) frequency range by Tao et al. (2008)[113]. Terahertz time-domain spectroscopy has been employed to study the metamaterial response. In this case, the operating frequency region was 0.25-2.5 THz with the polyimide substrate thickness as 5.5 μm . The transmission of the THz electric field was studied with air as the reference and for the SRR sample. The electric field spectral phase and amplitude were determined using the Fourier transformation. The simulated transmission determined the dielectric response, in which the samples represented negative dielectric constants and strong resonances above the resonant frequency. Using a hybrid mode solver, the cloak was further simulated in COSMOL Multiphysics S/w. The results clearly indicated that the cloak reduces the scattering in the

forward as well as the backward directions. Figure 7(b) indicates the fabricated metamaterial's mechanical flexibility wrapped around a glass bottle. Liu et al. experimentally demonstrated a broadband ground-plane cloak that could hide an object. The transformation space was realized using an optimization technique in which a quasi-conformal coordinate map was formed[114]. The cloak was embedded in a medium with a refractive index of 1.331. An additional impedance-matching layer was formed around the cloak. It was shown that this cloaking eliminated the backscattering and also restored the reflected beam. Here, the entire sample area was divided into a number of 2 by 2 mm squares, requiring 10000 elements among which 6000 were unique. Matlab was used to perform the generation of the regression curve and the final layout of the elements. The nature of the ground plane cloak was verified by using a phase-sensitive, near-field microwave scanning system to map the electric field distribution inside a planar waveguide. The cloaking structure indicated a very small loss over the operational frequency range of 13 to 18 GHz.

Gabrielli et al. demonstrated an optical invisibility cloak that could hide an object under a carpet with the help of a reflective surface.[115] The fabrication and the design of a cloaking device at the optical frequencies that was able to reshape the reflected image and provide the observer with an illusion of looking at a plane mirror was created. The operational wavelength was 1550 nm. The device with the triangular shape possessed an area of $225 \mu\text{m}^2$ with a hiding region of $1.6 \mu\text{m}^2$. The reflective surface possessed a distributed Bragg reflector (DBR) with alternating regions of crystalline silicon and SiO_2 . FDTD method was used to study the propagation of light in the device. The presence of the cloak and the image of the light incident on the deformation resembled the image of a wave without any deformation propagating in a homogeneous medium. Using TO, the opposite of cloaking, i.e., concentrating light in an area, could also be achieved. Li et al. designed a cylindrical cloak with a non-uniform LC network. The LC network had three branches for controlling the material parameters μ_r , μ_θ , and ϵ_z . [116] This cloak's response to a broadband EM pulse was further investigated experimentally. It was also realized that an anisotropic and inhomogeneous medium with material tensors on a cylindrical basis could be fabricated artificially by a non-periodic transmission line network. The operating frequency was 40 MHz. Kante et al. proposed a non-magnetic cloak by direct mapping of the magnetic field. The concealed region diameter was 4.4 wavelengths. The structure was based on the electric response of a split ring resonator (SRR) which was designed at a frequency of 11 GHz. The resin was used as a dielectric spacer with decreasing thickness from the outer layer to the inner layer of the cloak.[117] The mapping of a magnetic field was done using a loop antenna with a circular coil made up of an inner conductor of SMA cable

5.2. Superlenses

In recent years, there has been considerable interest in methods that could potentially surpass the classical diffraction limit, facilitating subwavelength imaging. Notably, the concept of the "perfect lens", has garnered significant attention due to its potential for achieving flawless imaging[118]. The superlens is constructed from a thin layer of material exhibiting either negative permittivity or permeability, or both. The superlens operates by restoring the evanescent spatial spectrum through the resonant excitation of surface waves. The first

experimental validation of a superlens took place in 2005. Fang et al. meticulously created an ultra-smooth silver film with an appropriate thickness, allowing it to function as a superlens for p-polarized light. Their experiments achieved a remarkable resolution of 89 nm, significantly smaller than the wavelength of the illuminating light ($\lambda=365$ nm)[119]. Although this super-resolution imaging was confined to a very limited near-field region captured by a photoresist, it undeniably represents the first experimental demonstration of optical superlens imaging based on John Pendry's groundbreaking concept. However, this superlens is unable to recover a super-resolution image at a distance from the lens interface unless the negative index material (with $n=-1$) has a thickness equal to the imaging distance, as per John Pendry's theory. This limitation effectively precludes the use of a single-layer metallic film for such applications.

Figure 8. (a) Schematic of the superlens imaging with a 35-nm silver film. (b) Imaging of an arbitrary object, “NANO,” by a silver superlens, with the upper panel fabricated in Cr film, middle showing the images by the Ag superlens, and bottom showing the projection results when the Ag superlens is replaced by a PMMA spacer. (c) Line information of the feature size taken by the Ag superlens and without it[120]

Recently, researchers have demonstrated that a structured material composed of an array of intersecting metallic wires possesses unique characteristics, including an unexpectedly high positive index of refraction[121]. This finding is intriguing, as one might intuitively assume that, in the long-wavelength limit, the material would not support propagating plane waves and would instead exhibit plasma like behavior. However, it was shown that this material does not exhibit negative permittivity; rather, it interacts with electromagnetic waves as if it has a significantly large positive permittivity. Specifically, a slab of this material can support ultrasubwavelength guided modes with very short guided wavelengths. These remarkable properties have been experimentally validated at microwave frequencies.

The implementation of a bulk negative index material (NIM) featuring simultaneous negative permittivity (ϵ) and permeability (μ) through subwavelength nano-range has been demonstrated to be highly difficult at optical wavelengths. Therefore, employing more continuous structures to construct the superlens presents a more viable approach. Theoretical investigations into an optical hyperlens have been suggested, utilizing an anisotropic medium characterized by hyperbolic dispersion. Consider an anisotropic medium with its permittivity tensor defined as follows.

$$\varepsilon = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \varepsilon_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.4)$$

Here, we define the medium as uniaxial with the axis along the z direction; further we rewrite $\varepsilon_z = \varepsilon_{||}$, $\varepsilon_x = \varepsilon_y = \varepsilon_{\perp}$. Substituting Eq. (5.4) into the Maxwell equation, we have an eigen function of

$$\left(\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \varepsilon_{\perp} - k^2\right) \left(\frac{\omega^4}{c^4} \varepsilon_{\perp} \varepsilon_{||} - \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \varepsilon_{\perp} (k_x^2 + k_y^2) - \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \varepsilon_{||} k_z^2\right) = 0 \quad (5.5)$$

Which possess 2 solutions as

$$\left(\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \varepsilon_{\perp} - k^2\right) = 0 \quad (5.6(a))$$

$$\left(\frac{\omega^4}{c^4} \varepsilon_{\perp} \varepsilon_{||} - \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \varepsilon_{\perp} (k_x^2 + k_y^2) - \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \varepsilon_{||} k_z^2\right) = 0 \quad (5.6(b))$$

Equation (5.6(a)) is an equation of ordinary wave with respect to the TE polarization, while Eq. (5.6(b)) indicates an extraordinary wave equation of TM polarization with a dispersion relation of

$$\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} = \frac{k_x^2 + k_z^2}{\varepsilon_{||} \varepsilon_{\perp}} \quad (5.7)$$

which is a well-defined hyperbolic dispersion if ε_{\perp} and $\varepsilon_{||}$ have opposite signs. It can be further classified into two types, depending on which component is negative as Figure 9 shows.

Figure 9. Schematic showing wave vectors and light propagation in a uniaxial media with principal dielectric constants of varying signs. (a) k space wave vector diagram with $\epsilon_{||} > 0$, $\epsilon_{\perp} < 0$. The solid hyperbola shows the propagating waves wave vectors in the uniaxial medium. The long solid arrow shows incident wave vector, dashed arrow signifies the reflected wave vector and the dashed-dotted arrow represents the transmitted wave vector, respectively. The short solid arrow shows the Poynting vector (S) of the transmitted wave. (b) Wave vector diagram for a uniaxial medium with $\epsilon_{\perp} > 0$, $\epsilon_{||} < 0$. (c), (d) Waves in real space for $\epsilon_{||} > 0$, $\epsilon_{\perp} < 0$ and $\epsilon_{||} < 0$, $\epsilon_{\perp} > 0$ respectively[120].

From Figure 9, it is evident that the phase and group velocities within hyperbolic metamaterials can be precisely tailored by adjusting the negative permittivity components alone, without the necessity for magnetic components. This advancement considerably simplifies the realization of negative index materials (NIM). Subsequently, various forms of negative refraction and super-resolution imaging at optical wavelengths have been successfully achieved, with flat lenses derived from such hyperbolic NIMs referred to as hyperlenses. For instance, Jie Yao and colleagues fabricated a silver nanowire array embedded in a dielectric matrix using the anodic alumina template method, successfully demonstrating negative refraction at an optical wavelength of 780 nm. According to Equation (5), the negative refractive index is contingent upon the polarization (e.g., TM polarization); the authors reported a negative index of -4.0 for TM-polarized light, which contrasts sharply with the effective refractive index of +2.2 for TE-polarized light, as determined through analysis of the refraction angle. Another notable NIM was presented in 2013 by Ting Xu and associates, who reported the experimental realization of a negative metamaterial operational at wavelengths extending into the ultraviolet range ($\lambda \sim 363.8$ nm). This was achieved through the use of stacked plasmonic waveguides, resulting in omnidirectional negative refraction for TM-polarized light. Although this multilayered NIM exhibits the flat-lens functionality predicted by Viktor G. Veselago, it still falls short of super-resolution capabilities due to imperfections in both sample fabrication and optical characterization. Nonetheless, Zhaowei Liu and his team previously overcame the challenge of achieving super-resolution imaging in the far field by developing a cylindrical hyperlens composed of metamaterials, which successfully imaged with a sub-diffraction resolution of 130 nm at a working wavelength of 365 nm. This cylindrical hyperlens is constructed by multilayering metal/dielectric units, which can magnify the object by converting scattered evanescent waves into the propagating waves, and hence projecting a high-resolution image into the far field[122].

5.3. Plasmonic metamaterials-based Surface-Enhanced Spectroscopy

5.3.1. Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering

Raman scattering is characterized as an inelastic scattering phenomenon where photons interact with molecules, leading to a frequency shift in the incident photons as a result of molecular excitation into elevated vibrational or rotational energy states. Unlike methods that detect molecules through variations in the local dielectric environment, Raman spectroscopy offers a unique spectral fingerprint for molecules, making it a valuable tool for material identification and analysis[123][124]. To address the inherently low cross section of Raman scattering, surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) has been developed, utilizing local field

enhancement from surface plasmons to significantly amplify Raman signals, achieving sensitivity down to the level of single molecules[125][126][127][128]. The engineering of spectral responses and local field enhancements provided by plasmonic materials presents a compelling substrate option for SERS spectroscopy, yielding notable signal enhancement along with excellent uniformity and reproducibility in the signals obtained[129][130][131][132]. In this section, we review the application of plasmonic metamaterials in SERS for molecular detection and analysis.

Over the past few decades, a variety of metamaterial-based SERS substrates have been developed. For instance, SRR metamaterials provide two transducing pathways that facilitate the simultaneous collection of quantitative binding information and distinctive biomolecular fingerprints[133]. Self-assembled plasmonic metamaterials at liquid/liquid or liquid/air interfaces enable the sensitive SERS-based detection of multiple analytes from aqueous, organic, or gaseous phases[134]. An investigation utilizing an array of silver nanorods revealed a significant correlation between the SERS signal and the geometry of the metamaterial, demonstrating an increase in SERS intensity by more than 200 times when the inter-rod gap distance was reduced from 35 nm to 10 nm.[135] This phenomenon is attributed to the enhancement of electromagnetic fields in the spaces between adjacent nanorods as the inter-rod gap narrows. Additionally, the use of elevated gold bowtie nanoantenna arrays with a gap thickness of approximately 7.5 nm resulted in substantial SERS enhancement factors exceeding 10^{11} (Figure 10(a)). This enhancement is ascribed to the significantly amplified local fields within the nanoantenna gap and the elevated structure, which can yield up to two orders of magnitude additional enhancement in the SERS response due to its radiation efficiency (Figure 10(b))[136]. Generally, SERS signals exhibit a marked increase as the distance between plasmonic components decreases, owing to the enhancement of the local field; however, this trend reverses at distances smaller than approximately 1 nm, where local field enhancement is compromised by the onset of electron tunneling[137].

Figure 10. SERS based molecular detection using plasmonic metamaterials substrate. (a) SEM image of a 3D gold bow tie nanoantenna with of $8 (\pm 1)$ nm gap. (b) Comparison of spectra of *p*-mercaptoaniline with elevated and nonelevated bow tie substrates. (c) SEM image of plasmonic gold nanohole array/SiO₂ spacer/gold film with the inset indicating picture of the

metamaterial sample. (d) SERS image of the structure obtained using 1580 cm^{-1} peak intensity of benzenethiol. (e) SERS intensity mapping (1621 cm^{-1}) of the metasurface after the Raman probe (crystal violet, 10^{-5} M). treatment (Inset indicating TEM image of a plasmonic metasurface made from silver nanocube array). (f) Schematic showing the working of the sweat extraction system and (g) Integrated sensor based real-time monitoring of nicotine in human skin with sweat extraction. [96]

Unlike the conventional SERS substrates, metamaterial-based SERS substrates possess good reproducibility and control in fabrication, providing reproducible and uniform SERS signals over a vast area required for the application purposes[138]. Plasmonic metamaterials were formed by gold nanohole array/SiO₂ spacer/gold film structures (Figure 10©) using holographic lithography for SERS detection with high uniformity.[138] The size of the metamaterial-SERS sensing area could be as large as 10 mm (inset of Figure 10©), along with the mapping of the metamaterial on various areas of $40 \times 40\ \mu\text{m}^2$ shows a high SERS uniformity (Figure 10(d)). The RSD of the measured signal was calculated as 12.6% [139]. A Langmuir–Blodgett self-assembly approach was used to develop periodic silver nanocube superlattice metafilm (inset of Figure 10(e) on a flexible polymer substrate. Here interestingly, the RSD of the SERS signal was demonstrated to be $\sim 3.9\%$ (Figure 10(e)), suggesting an excellent reproducibility and huge potential for commercial applications.[140] This plasmonic metamaterial when integrated along a flexible electronic system was able to automatically extract sweat and other analytes from the human body (Figure 10(f)). This formed the basis for a wearable sensing platform with strong molecular recognition capability. (Figure 10(g)) shows the real-time monitoring of drug nicotine in human skin with the integrated electronic wearable sensor.

5.3.2. Surface-Enhanced Infrared Absorption

Infrared (IR) absorption spectroscopy is another technique for the molecular detection through their vibrational fingerprints. Surface-enhanced infrared absorption (SEIRA) is a phenomenon which can highly increase the IR absorption of the molecules through either molecular dipole enhancement or surface plasmon-enhanced light-molecule interactions[141]. It was first shown using thin metal films having molecular[142]. SEIRA was subsequently widely investigated using various roughened metal surfaces or metal-island films[143]. Since the plasmonic response of these nanostructures usually lies in the visible spectral range, the mechanism of the observed SEIRA effects can be easily explained using the excitation of vibrations of the absorbed molecules via induced fields of the metal islands[144]. Also, by tailoring the material and the geometry of meta-atoms as well as their corresponding near-field coupling, the optical response of these plasmonic metamaterials can be easily tuned into the near- and mid-IR spectrum to obtain strong field enhancement. Therefore, plasmonic metamaterials gives an ideal platform for the SEIRA spectroscopy with enhanced sensitivity.

A variety of metal-based plasmonic metamaterials like SRRs,[145] nanoantenna arrays[146], metallic hole arrays,[147] have been explored for the SEIRA applications with high reproducibility and strong signal enhancement. Significant efforts have been made on the fabrication of the SEIRA substrates with strong local fields and, hence, high sensitivity.[147]

Using an SRR array having high near-field enhancement in the gap, IR detection with zeptomole-level sensitivity was studied.[145] A monolayer of biomolecules was detected using a gold nanoantenna array over a gold layer, providing a SEIRA signal four times higher compared to a nonresonant metamaterial[148]. The detection sensitivity is improved due to the enhanced electromagnetic fields formed between gold ground layer and the cross nanoantenna. The operating frequencies for plasmonic metamaterials in SEIRA are commonly fixed after the fabrication, despite the requirement of selective detection of multiband molecular vibrational modes over a broad IR range. The resonating frequency can be tuned in a broad spectral range, by integrating the metamaterials with a flexible substrate by applying certain mechanical force, to cover different vibrational modes of the molecule[149]. Detection of different spectral fingerprints of varying moieties was investigated simultaneously with SEIRA which could provide a better signal for the identification of molecules. A dual-band perfect absorber with a 4 nm thick PMMA layer based on a gold nanocross metamaterial was used in order to achieve 2 molecular vibrational modes detection. In a different instance, the use of a Fano-resonant asymmetric metamaterial, characterized by sharp resonances resulting from the interference between subradiant and superradiant plasmonic resonances (as illustrated in Figure 11(a)), facilitated the quantitative biosensing and fingerprinting of nanometer-scale multimolecular nanoassemblies.[150] The vibrational fingerprints, such as the amide I and II bands of proteins, from the protein A/G monolayer (depicted in Figure 11(b)) and the bilayer of protein A/G and IgG antibodies (shown in Figure 11(c)), were distinctly identified with significant signal enhancement. Furthermore, the simultaneous detection of various spectral fingerprints from different components using Surface-Enhanced Infrared Absorption (SEIRA) can be achieved through plasmonic metamaterials that exhibit broadband resonance in the mid-infrared range. By self-assembling plasmonic nanoshells that resonate in the near-infrared into a two-dimensional periodic array with interparticle gaps of less than 10 nanometers, a concurrent enhancement of Raman scattering and infrared absorption was accomplished. In these densely packed nanoshell arrays, the multipolar plasmon resonances of individual nanoshells hybridize, resulting in a relatively narrow resonance in the visible or near-infrared spectrum due to the coupled quadrupolar nanoshell resonances, which provides a Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) enhancement factor in the range of 10^8 to 10^9 . Additionally, a broad mid-infrared resonance (approximately 2–8 μm) emerges from the coupled dipolar resonances, enhancing SEIRA by a factor of around 10^4 [151]. The integration of infrared plasmonic metamaterials with a microfluidic chamber enables real-time and in situ SEIRA characterization of biomolecules in aqueous solutions, which holds significant potential for practical applications.

Figure 11. SEIRA spectroscopy involving plasmonic metamaterials. (a) Schematic showing charge distributions for the superradiant (D) and subradiant (Q) and modes of a Fano-resonant asymmetric metamaterial. Data obtained for (b) Protein A/G monolayer and (c) Protein A/G + IgG antibody bilayer using varying asymmetric metamaterial-based pixels. (d) Graphene mid-infrared biosensor. (e) SEM image showing graphene nanoribbon array with a width 30nm and a period of 80 nm respectively. (f) Extinction spectra of graphene nanoribbon array for varying bias voltage V_g after (solid curves) and before (dashed curves) protein bilayer formation. Gray vertical strips show the amide I and II vibrational bands of protein. [96]

Recently, graphene has emerged as an interesting material for plasmonics showing strong active tunability and optical confinement of spectral response[151-152] that are important for mid-IR plasmon-enhanced IR spectroscopy.[153] Therefore, highly sensitivity detection of vibrational fingerprints and refractive index of biomolecules were obtained using graphene metamaterials.[151] Figure 11(d,e) shows schematic of, the plasmon excited across the nanoribbons upon IR illumination, which strongly enhances the interaction of the protein molecules adsorbed on the graphene surface. Experimentally, graphene plasmons present in a nanoribbon array showed higher sensitivity in the protein bilayer detection both in SEIRA and transmission spectroscopies (Figure 11(f)).

6. Conclusion

The field of plasmonic metamaterials is growing rapidly and it will continuously advance. The integration of plasmonics and metamaterials leads to several benefits, rendering the plasmonic metamaterials a promising platform to study complex optical effects and new applications for example, the large local field enhancement causing stronger light-matter interaction, through which many weak techniques can be effectively enhanced and utilized. Secondly, the ultrafast optical and the tight field confinement processes enable the development of miniaturized devices, working either as the bridge of electronic and photonic components, or even the optical photonic circuits. Thirdly, the plasmonic metamaterials spectra are strongly tunable by altering the individual constituent's response and their

coupling. This is strongly desirable in nearly all the practical situations. Owing to the above attractive features, plasmonic metamaterials are expected to extend their horizon beyond the fundamental applications discussed in this chapter. In terms of the fundamental interaction of molecular plasmonics with metamaterials, several new fields are currently emerging for example the development of certain new types of plasmonic metamaterials for the molecular plasmonics, such as topological insulator-based metamaterials and the quantum plasmonic metamaterials. Particularly, exploitation and understanding of quantum and nonlocal molecular plasmonics may create novel avenues across all the application areas, including engineered lasing and spontaneous emission, biochemical sensing and light modulation. The development and design of new plasmonic materials such as conducting and semiconductor oxides in order to extend the spectral range of hot-electron generation and light absorption is important for the optimal utilization of solar spectrum. Research in the field of ultra strong coupling of molecules with the plasmonic excitations is leading to progress in fundamental understanding of physics of these processes and enhancement of the existing practical applications.

Despite the advanced technicalities in the understanding and designing involved, plasmonic metamaterials will rapidly continue to advance for the development of future photonic and plasmonic applications including ultrahigh-sensitivity optical sensing, active functionalities, nanolasers, and photoactuated nanochemistry, as a versatile platform that can enhance and manipulate optical phenomena on the nanoscale.

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